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**BUDGETARY RESOURCES MARKET:
 A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF APPROACHES AND AUTHOR’S DEFINITION**

The subject of this study is the theoretical conceptualization of the budgetary resources market as a specific segment of the financial system, not reducible to the mechanical sum of debt, transfer, and procurement procedures. The aim of the work is to conduct a comparative analysis of established methodological approaches in financial science, construct a static three-segment model of market architecture, visualize a dynamic model of the cyclical interaction of its components, and formulate an integrated author’s definition based on this. The methodological foundation is formed by systems and dialectical approaches, allowing for the consideration of budgetary relations within the unity of their distributive and quasi-market nature. The study identifies and critically analyzes three key paradigms: administrative-fund, segmental-market, and institutional-distributive. The scientific novelty lies in the development of two original frameworks that reveal the morphology and cyclical dynamics of the market, as well as in the formulation of a definition that synthesizes the debt, transfer, and contractual components into a single space with its inherent mechanisms of limited competition. The obtained results form the theoretical basis for the subsequent development of a typology of financial markets based on the criterion of the dominant type of interest.

Keywords: budget resource market, public finance, budget, resource allocation, public interest, quasi-market mechanisms, interbudgetary relations.

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